

Checklist to assess your current and aspirational FAIR-enabling capabilities

The FAIR Principles focus on characteristics of digital objects that make them Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. Achieving and maintaining those characteristics depends on the individuals and organisations that create, store, curate, and preserve the objects. These activities are 'FAIR-enabling', and repositories and data service providers play an important role in facilitating them. This tool is developed to self-assess the current and aspirational FAIR-enabling capabilities of your organisation, to assist in defining focus areas in the FAIR Implementation Action Plan.

How to use the self-assessment checklist

The self-assessment checklist addresses the five aspects regarding repository or data service provider that are covered in the resources and support of the Support Programme:

1. Policy
2. FAIR data assessment
3. Supporting the FAIRness of objects
4. Displaying trustworthiness
5. Engaging with your community

Please consider all aspects and their accompanying self-assessment questions. First, consider the level of achievement that has been reached in the **current state** of your repository or data service in column *Current*. Depending on the kind of data service you provide, not all aspects or statements may be relevant for you.

Assess your current capabilities

- How aware are you about the FAIR principles?
- How fair-enabling are your practices currently?
- What FAIR-enabling services and support do you currently provide?
- What are the gaps in the FAIR-enabling services?

If you judge that Level 1 has not been attained for any of the questions below, then enter 'Level 0' in the 'Current' column.

Next, consider which aspects you would like to **improve** and mark them in column *Aspiration*. In the next stages of the support programme this will help you to choose FAIR-enabling resources and formulate your Action Plan.

Answer options are formulated according to different types, presented in this table:

Answer option types	
	Select the most appropriate maturity level
	Tick the relevant boxes (multiple choice)

Self-assessment questions

1. Policy

To implement FAIR-enabling activities in an organisation, it is important to include these desires in the core policies. Ideally, the service/organisation policy or mission statement is published and explicitly aligned with principles for FAIR and Open Science.

The checklist for this topic is based on Key issue #1 in Assessing Capability Maturity and Engagement with FAIR-enabling Practices (ACME-FAIR)¹

Remember, if Level 1 has not been attained, then you have the option of entering 'Level 0' in the 'Current' column.

1a. The policy or mission statement of our repository or service organisation...			<i>Current</i>	<i>Aspiration</i>
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	<i>Selected level:</i>	<i>Selected level:</i>
... addresses the importance of managing data according to FAIR principles.	... articulates the need for sustainable access and long-term preservation of research data, to keep data FAIR and ensure research integrity.	...assesses research outputs and/or Open Science practices with emphasis on identifying areas for improvement, with recommendations covering measures to enable FAIR.	<i>Evidence:</i>	<i>Reasoning:</i>

¹ Joy Davidson, Angus Whyte, Laura Molloy, Marjan Grootveld, & Mark Thorley. (2022). Defining the Policy Environment: ACME-FAIR Issue #1 (2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6345332>

1b. Our policy document or mission statement itself is machine-actionable.			<i>Current</i>	<i>Aspiration</i>
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	<i>Selected level:</i>	<i>Selected level:</i>
The policy is online, with clear indicators of its currency.	The policy has an identifier and structured markup to support machine-readability.	The policy is registered in relevant community catalogues of FAIR-enabling resources.	<i>Evidence:</i>	<i>Reasoning:</i>

2. FAIR data assessment

Assessing the FAIRness of objects provides snapshot insights into the FAIRness of the object at the moment. It can function as a starting point of planning to improve the FAIRness of objects by making changes for the specific object or the FAIR-enabling activities the organisation executes for all objects. Effective automated assessment requires that certain information is available and accessible for machines.

The checklist for this topic consists of a selection of metrics from the FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics (V0.5)². For integrity's sake, we have kept the formulations true to their source. Discussions on what each metrics means for your specific organisation can be noted down to help formulate realistic areas of focus for the later Action Plan. A full execution of an automated FAIR assessment tool can be undertaken during the implementation phase of the programme.

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 2a. The following holds for data and metadata in our service:		<i>Current</i>		<i>Aspiration</i>	
		<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Evidence:</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Reasoning:</i>
FsF-F1-01D	Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Evidence:</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Reasoning:</i>
FsF-F4-01M	Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved by machines.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Evidence:</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Reasoning:</i>
FsF-F2-01M	Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Evidence:</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Reasoning:</i>

² Devaraju, A., Huber, R., Mokrane, M., Herterich, P., Cepinskas, L., de Vries, J., L'Hours, H., Davidson, J., & Angus White. (2022). FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics (0.5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6461229>

FsF-A1-01M	Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Evidence:</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Reasoning:</i>
FsF-I1-01M	Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language. Examples of knowledge representation languages are RDF, RDFS, and OWL.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Evidence:</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Reasoning:</i>
FsF-R1.3-02D	Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Evidence:</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Reasoning:</i>
FsF-R1.2-01M	Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Evidence:</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Reasoning:</i>
FsF-R1.1-01M	Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Evidence:</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Reasoning:</i>
NA	Not applicable: we don't hold data or metadata	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Evidence:</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Reasoning:</i>

2b. (FAIR) Signposting is implemented in our organisation³. <i>Remember, if Level 1 has not been attained, then you have the option of entering 'Level 0' in the 'Current' column.</i>			<i>Current</i>	<i>Aspiration</i>
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	<i>Selected:</i>	<i>Selected:</i>
We have considered FAIR Signposting, but implementation is not in process	The implementation is in progress	Yes, signposting is implemented in our repository or data service.	<i>Evidence:</i>	<i>Reasoning:</i>

³ FAIR Signposting is a method to expose machine-actionable navigation links that indicate downloadable resources, types and attribution – particularly for scholarly and institutional repositories which use persistent identifiers like DOIs. Read more at: <https://signposting.org/FAIR/>

3. Supporting the FAIRness of objects

Alongside the use of automated assessment tools for gaining insights into the current FAIRness level of objects, there are various ways to increase or otherwise support the FAIRness of objects in a repository or data service.

The checklist for this topic is based on Key issue #6 in Assessing Capability Maturity and Engagement with FAIR-enabling Practices (ACME-FAIR)⁴

Remember, if Level 1 has not been attained, then you have the option of entering 'Level 0' in the 'Current' column.

3a. Data producers benefit from advice about which data to archive and how to prepare the data to optimise reusability.			<i>Current</i>	<i>Aspiration</i>
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	<i>Selected level:</i>	<i>Selected level:</i>
We offer guidance for selecting data to comply with funder requirements, or for legal and regulatory reasons.	We offer criteria for research projects to select data and related outputs of long-term value, to be made FAIR as a priority, and for estimating costs of FAIR data preparation and the benefits that may be gained.	We offer measurable objectives for building collections of FAIR data and related research outputs that meet identified use cases for data reusers.	<i>Evidence:</i>	<i>Reasoning:</i>
3b. Publishing metadata is essential to inform potential data consumers about future use.			<i>Current</i>	<i>Aspiration</i>

⁴ Angus Whyte, Marjan Grootveld, Maaïke Verburg, & René van Horik. (2022). Selecting Data, Services, and Repositories for FAIR: ACME-FAIR Issue #6 (2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6345114>

<p><i>Remember, if Level 1 has not been attained, then you have the option of entering 'Level 0' in the 'Current' column.</i></p>				
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	<i>Selected level:</i>	<i>Selected level:</i>
We apply standards for data citation and discovery metadata, and assign persistent identifiers (PIDs) to data.	Level 1 + with metadata inter-linked with related outputs.	Level 2 + we publish (meta)data on all publicly-funded research outputs of long-term value, using community-recognised controlled vocabularies.	<i>Evidence:</i>	<i>Reasoning:</i>

4. Displaying trustworthiness

For potential users to make informed decisions about how they interact with repositories and data service providers, it is important that they can develop a sense of trust in the service and organisation. To this end, it is important for the service provider to display their trustworthiness clearly and transparently to the outside world, ideally in a way that both humans and machines can understand.

The checklist for this topic consists of a selection of CoreTrustSeal requirements for trustworthy data repositories⁵. CoreTrustSeal offers a certification service, but organisations can also use the requirements and guidance internally, without (yet) aiming for certification. Not all service providers are in scope for CoreTrustSeal certification, so not all requirements may be applicable to your organisation. This does not mean the organisation is less trustworthy, as long as it is clearly communicated which practices are and are not to be expected from the organisation and why. Transparency is key.

4a. Continuity of service: We have a plan to ensure ongoing access to and preservation of data and metadata. [CTS R3]				<i>Current</i>	<i>Aspiration</i>
Level 0	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	<i>Selected level:</i>	<i>Selected level:</i>
No, we have not considered this	To some extent (e.g., we are currently discussing potential implementation, or are drafting a plan)	We have considered this and implemented it to the extent that is relevant to our organisation (e.g., a fully documented plan, or clearly supported decision to not have such a plan)	Level 3 + We have clearly and publicly communicated this to potential users (e.g., provided a link or statement on our website)	<i>Evidence:</i>	<i>Reasoning:</i>

⁵ Specifically, the CoreTrustSeal Requirements for the period of 2023-2025. For more information, see: <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

4b. Preservation plan: we assume responsibility for long-term preservation and manage this function in a planned and documented way. [CTS R9]				<i>Current</i>	<i>Aspiration</i>
Level 0	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	<i>Selected level:</i>	<i>Selected level:</i>
No, we have not considered this	To some extent (e.g., we are currently discussing potential implementation, or are drafting a plan)	We have considered this and implemented it to the extent that is relevant to our organisation (e.g., a fully documented plan, or clearly supported decision to not have such a plan)	Level 3 + We have clearly and publicly communicated this to potential users (e.g., provided a link or statement on our website)	<i>Evidence:</i>	<i>Reasoning:</i>

5. Engaging with your community

Repositories and data services have various stakeholders, some of whom ‘produce’ or ‘consume’ data. We use ‘community’ in a broad sense, which at least includes researchers. If you do not currently have a sense of who your community is, this will be explored later in the creation of the Engagement strategy.

The checklist for this topic is based on Do I-PASS for FAIR. A self assessment tool to measure the FAIR-ness of an organisation⁶ (6a) and on Key issue #1 in Assessing Capability Maturity and Engagement with FAIR-enabling Practices (ACME-FAIR)⁷ (6b).

Remember, if Level 1 has not been attained, then you have the option of entering ‘Level 0’ in the ‘Current’ column.

6a. To communicate our service policies (e.g. data acquisition policy or preservation policy) we use the following means and channels:			<i>Current</i>	<i>Aspiration</i>
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	<i>Selected level:</i>	<i>Selected level:</i>
We have a website that contains all information, and in addition we have a central (online) point of contact.	Level 1 + we provide regular workshops, webinars and training events.	Level 2 + new researchers are informed of the policy or policies upon arrival.	<i>Evidence:</i>	<i>Reasoning:</i>
6b. We engage with users and stakeholders in our service development in the following ways:			<i>Current</i>	<i>Aspiration</i>

⁶ Taco de Bruin, Sarah Coombs, Jutta de Jong, Irene Haslinger, Henk van den Hoogen, Frans Huigen, Mijke Jetten, Jacko Koster, Margriet Miedema, Sjef Öllers, Inge Slouwerhof, Ingeborg Verheul, & Jacquelijin Ringersma. (2020). Do I-PASS for FAIR. A self assessment tool to measure the FAIR-ness of an organization (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4080867>

⁷ Joy Davidson, Angus Whyte, Laura Molloy, Marjan Grootveld, & Mark Thorley. (2022). Defining the Policy Environment: ACME-FAIR Issue #1 (2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6345332>

Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	<i>Selected level:</i>	<i>Selected level:</i>
We gather (community) requirements for enabling support of FAIR and Open Research, and for long-term access to research data.	Level 1 + we analyse service requirements and gaps to fulfil them, and we support practitioners to embed (community) practice locally.	Level 2 + we consult and collaborate extensively with community representatives.	<i>Evidence:</i>	<i>Reasoning:</i>